

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

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THE CONCEPT OF ILLICIT DRUG TRAFFICKING AND PSYCHOTROPIC SUBSTANCES

ANNOTATION

The fight against drug addiction is given top priority both ideologically and in legislative and law enforcement practice. However, constant changes in legislation and regulations, as well as in judicial and investigative practice, are often not as effective as expected.

Analysis of the results of this activity shows that a number of these changes are aimed not at strengthening the fight against drug crime, but at weakening it, and creates preferences for the most dangerous drug criminals.

Key words: fight against crime, narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, potent and toxic substances, precursors, decriminalization, drug addiction.

ГИЁХВАНД МОДДАЛАРНИНГ НОҚОНУНИЙ АЙЛАНИШИ ТУШУНЧАСИ ВА ПСИХОТРОП МОДДАЛАР

АННОТАЦИЯ

Гиёхвандликка қарши курашишда биринчи навбатта эътиборни мафкуравий ва ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиётига қаратилади. Бирок, қонунчилик ва меъёрий ҳужжатлардаги, шунингдек, суд ва тергов амалиётидаги доимий ўзгаришлар кўпинча қутилган даражада самарали эмас.

Мазкур фаолият натижалари таҳлили шуни кўрсатадики, мазкур ўзгаришларнинг бир қисми гиёхвандликка қарши курашишни кучайтиришга эмас, балки заифлаштиришга қаратилган бўлиб, ўта хавfli жиноятчилар учун қулайликлар яратмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: жиноятчилик, гиёхвандлик воситалари, психотроп моддалар, кучли таъсир этувчи ва захарли моддалар, прекурсорлар, декриминализация, гиёхвандликка қарши курашиш.

ПОНЯТИЕ НЕЗАКОННОГО ОБОРОТА НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ И ПСИХОТРОПНЫХ ВЕЩЕСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Борьбе с наркотизмом уделяется первостепенное внимание как в идеологическом плане, так и в законодательной и правоприменительной практике. Однако постоянные изменения в законодательстве и подзаконных актах, а также в судебно-следственной практике зачастую оказываются не столь эффективны, как ожидается.

Анализ результатов данной деятельности показывает, что целый ряд этих изменений направлен не на усиление борьбы с наркопреступностью, а на ее ослабление, и создает преференции для наиболее опасных наркопреступников.

Ключевые слова: борьба с преступностью, наркотические средства, психотропные вещества, сильнодействующие и ядовитые вещества, прекурсоры, декриминализация, наркомания.

Among the most acute, global, intractable and dangerous social problems for the whole world that have recently worried the world community, threatening people's health and life itself on earth, first of all, include drug addiction, narcotism, and AIDS.

The consequences of these negative phenomena have reached alarming proportions. Currently, the spread of drugs, drug addiction, drug addiction and drug trafficking is not restrained by strict laws, state borders are not stopped, and almost no prohibitive measures are restrained.

Drugs overcome any obstacles with enviable ease, stubbornly "spread", "seizing" large territories, "fishing out" more and more new victims. Today there are millions of people who have died from drug addiction and addiction. The illegality of drug trafficking means that such trafficking is carried out in violation of the laws on narcotic drugs.

The use of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors for controlled delivery and operational purchase, operational experiment, sampling for the study of these drugs and substances, and other operational investigative activities by operational units of law enforcement agencies, which, according to the law, have the right to carry out operational investigative activities, is permitted without a license.

For medical reasons, citizens are allowed to store and transport certain narcotic drugs purchased only with a doctor's prescription.

Illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs and precursors includes such illegal actions as their production, acquisition, storage, transportation, shipment, and cultivation of drug-containing plants [1].

Depending on their sources of origin, it is advisable to divide narcotic drugs into three groups:

1) narcotic drugs of plant origin are divided into:

a) obtained from various types of poppy plants;

b) obtained from hemp (marijuana, hashish, hashish oil);

2) drugs of synthetic origin, which include substances not found in nature, at the same time, in most cases, they are structural analogues of drugs of natural origin. Some of them are used in medicine as medicines.

The most common are plevitin, methadone, phencyclidine, trimethylfentanyl, LSD, structural analogues of mescaline and amphetamine - DOM, DOV, TMA, STP, etc.; drugs of semi-synthetic origin, which are made from a natural alkaloid by simple transcription. These include heroin, hydromorphone, oxycodone, etorphine and diprenorphine, derived from thebaine, etc.

The most common is heroin, one of the opium derivatives, obtained by a chemical reaction (acetylation) from morphine. Poppy straw, raw opium, marijuana, hashish, LSD, methadone, heroin, and ecstasy are widely used as drugs in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The emergence of new synthetic drugs poses a particular danger.

Recently, there has been a transition to "hard" drugs (opium, heroin, cocaine), as well as synthetic drugs (phetamine, amphetamine, etc.). Drug abuse leads to drug addiction.

Drug addiction is a painful mental condition caused by chronic intoxication due to drug abuse, referred to as such conventions by the UN or a specially authorized executive body in the field of health care, and characterized by mental or physical dependence on them [2].

Today, in order to correctly assess the drug situation, it is necessary to consider the historical aspect. Drugs have been known for a long time, and at all stages of development, humanity is faced with the problems of manufacturing, using and distributing drugs. History claims that attitudes towards drugs have never been straightforward.

Disagreements in the legislation of different countries sometimes reach the point of opposites. For example, in the USA, absolute intolerance for drug use is proclaimed; in France, such actions are punishable by imprisonment for a term of at least 2 months. up to 1 year and a large fine, in Greece from 2 to 5 years, in Switzerland from 1 to 3 months and a fine [3].

There is no unambiguous approach to the sanctions provided for the manufacture and distribution of narcotic drugs. So, in India, Bangladesh, Indonesia, Iran, Malaysia, North Korea, Thailand, Turkey, Egypt, China, Saudi Arabia and the like - the death penalty (hanging or shooting). In some countries, corporal punishment is also common, which is usually an “addition” to life imprisonment, imprisonment or a fine.

Despite the controversial approach to this problem, global practice has accumulated significant experience in combating negative social phenomena associated with drug trafficking. However, the fight against these phenomena requires not only joint action, but also a clear definition and distinction between the concepts of “drug abuse” and “drug addiction.”

There is no single approach to defining the content of the term “drug addiction” both among scientists and in the specialized literature. So, A.A. Gabiani defines “drug addiction” as a disease resulting from the systematic non-medical use of drugs [4].

A.A. Miroshnichenko, A.A. Muzyka define “drug addiction” (in legal terms) as a socially dangerous phenomenon, which is not only a disease that occurs as a result of intoxication and poisoning of the human body with drugs, but also one that, which is characterized by illegal actions of a person related to narcotic drugs, the circulation of which is controlled by a special international legal and domestic regime, aimed at protecting public health and socialist legal order.

The definition of drug addiction in the legal aspect cannot be limited only to such a sign as human disease. Together with this element (or independently of it), a true definition should generally reflect a socially dangerous phenomenon, which is also characterized by the illegality of various acts of the perpetrator with narcotic drugs [5].

Drug crime, as a manifestation of the problem, is characterized by the ability to degenerate into new, more dangerous forms. Drug addiction and drug addiction have never existed in isolation; they are interconnected with such negative “background phenomena and processes as alcoholism, substance abuse, prostitution, homelessness, etc.

Drug crimes are committed in an area where there is a well-established system of illegal activities for the production, transportation, and sale of narcotic drugs carried out by all participants in the criminal process.

The results of the study indicate that today in the Republic of Uzbekistan there is an extensive drug trafficking network, the criminal activities of which involve organized groups with representatives of international drug addiction.

Communication with representatives of the international mafia creates favorable conditions and provides an opportunity for criminal groups operating in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and having a stable source of enrichment to pump “dirty money” received from the sale of drugs abroad and their further legalization.

Drug trafficking is one of the most profitable criminal industries. Criminal organizations and individuals direct their activities to the spread of illicit drug trafficking, find new forms and methods of drug distribution, and involve a significant number of people in their use.

This leads to a further aggravation of the crime situation in the country. Criminal drug addiction is becoming a real threat that undermines the national security of our state and creates very serious problems for the international community.

The geopolitical position of our state makes it a kind of crossroads on the routes of international drug trafficking, and the lack of reliably protected state borders, intensive population migration, and cargo flows contribute to an increase in the flow of imported drugs into the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today we can say that the network of artisanal production of synthetic drugs is expanding in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Synthetic drugs and psychotropic substances are gradually replacing acetylated and extracted opium and hashish, traditional for the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In recent years, the number of crimes related to the distribution and abuse of drugs has been constantly growing. When carrying out targeted measures, law enforcement officers seize a large amount of handicraft and industrial drugs, especially during checks of persons, their luggage, suspicious objects, as well as during the liquidation of homemade drug laboratories and the like.

In their works, criminologists considered the issues of classifying drug crimes as criminal liability, and improved the construction of individual offenses. Criminologists studied drug crime, gave a criminological description of crimes related to drug trafficking, as well as the persons committing them, clarified the determinants, and proposed preventive measures.

Among others, the subject of criminological research is the illegal production of narcotic drugs. The exclusive right to organize and control the legal circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances belongs to the state, which is a monopolist in this area.

Scientists schematically view the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances as a set of several technologically interdependent stages. In particular, V.A. Timoshenko, V.B. Ivashenko, M.S. The group is talking about the production, transportation (delivery) and sale of narcotic drugs (sales) [6].

A similar point of view is shared by A.A. Besedin: cultivation (harvesting) - production, transportation - trade for profit [7].

As a rule, the sale of drugs does not occur in the place where they were manufactured or purchased. They move to sales markets located mainly in large cities. Considering this circumstance, in the opinion of L.V. Dorosh, Yu.V. Baulin, the scheme of illegal drug trafficking is as follows: production-transfer-sale of narcotic drugs-legalization of criminal proceeds.

Some researchers divide illicit drug trafficking into: cultivation-production-trade for profit [8].

Despite certain structural differences in the illegal drug trafficking chain, its obligatory element is the drug sales link. To summarize, we can conclude that drug trafficking includes three technologically related conditional blocks: production and sale (sale) of narcotic drugs - legalization of criminal proceeds.

At the same time, the key link in this chain is the sale or sale of narcotic drugs. Illegal drug trafficking as an object of influence of operational units of law enforcement agencies is actions related to the illegal cultivation, production, acquisition, storage, transportation, and transfer of narcotic drugs.

The study of the concept of drug trafficking and the use of funds obtained from illicit drug trafficking and re-invested in the process of illicit drug trafficking deserves special attention.

Illicit drug trafficking determines the existence of drug crime as an independent type of crime, for the definition of which it is necessary to be guided by the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and special laws and by-laws.

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